

Research Article

Effectiveness of Activated Bentonite as an Adsorbent for Zinc and Lead Ions

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Abstract: Heavy metal contamination in water resources cause a serious threat to environmental and health in urban area. Zinc and lead are the most common toxic heavy metals that do not break naturally and can cause long-term health problem to communities. Addressing these issues requires a low-cost, effective, and consistent solution for wastewater treatment. This study investigates the efficiency of bentonite clay—specifically raw and thermally activated forms—as an adsorbent for removing zinc (Zn^{2+}) and lead (Pb^{2+}) ions from aqueous solutions. Three types of bentonites were tested: raw (RB), activated at 300°C (AB300), and activated at 400°C (AB400). Adsorption experiments were conducted using a magnetic stirrer process, with 50 ppm of heavy metal solutions and bentonite doses ranging from 0.5 g to 1.1 g. Stirring durations were set at 30 and 60 minutes. Removal efficiency was determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) analysis. The results showed that thermal activation significantly enhanced bentonite’s adsorption performance, particularly at 400°C. For lead removal at 60 minutes and 1.1 g dosage, activated bentonite at 400°C achieved a peak removal efficiency of 99.6%. Similarly, zinc removal reached 75.9% under the same conditions. These findings show the potential of using thermally activated bentonite as a sustainable and economically practical solution for industrial and municipal wastewater treatment. This approach offers strong commercialization chances due to its local availability, low processing cost and high effectiveness especially for regions seeking affordable water purification technologies aligned with environmental protection goals.

Keywords: adsorption; bentonite; heavy metals; wastewater.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Water pollution caused by heavy metals has arisen a critical environmental and public health problems especially due to the industrial discharge of metals such as zinc (Zn^{2+}) and lead (Pb^{2+}). These metals are non-decomposable, and toxic even at low concentrations which lead to serious health issues.

For example, neurological damage, kidney dysfunction, and developmental disorders (Munir et al., 2022). Out of various wastewater treatment process, adsorption has gained interest due to its ease of application, effectiveness, and cost-efficiency (Pizutti et al., 2019).

Bentonite clay is a naturally occurring aluminosilicate which demonstrated excellent potential as an adsorbent due to its high surface area, cation exchange capacity, and availability. Raw bentonite requires activation to enhance its physical and chemical properties for more effective adsorption process (Ouyang et al., 2019). Thermal treatment is a cost-effective method of activation which can alters the surface structure and increases the number of active sites. Therefore, it is significantly improving the clay's capacity to adsorb metal ions (Wang et al., 2024).

This study focuses on evaluating the adsorption efficiency of three (3) forms of bentonite clay, 1) raw, 2) thermally activated at 300°C, and 3) thermally activated at 400°C—for the removal of zinc and lead ions from aqueous solutions. Using a magnetic stirrer method, the effects of contact time and bentonite dosage on removal efficiency were examined. The treated samples were analysed using Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) spectroscopy to determine residual metal concentrations. The findings aim to support the development of a low-cost, locally available, and scalable solution for heavy metal removal in water treatment systems especially in resource-limited settings.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study adopted bentonite clay as the adsorbent material for the removal of heavy metals such as zinc (Zn^{2+}) and lead (Pb^{2+}), from liquid solutions. Three types of bentonites were prepared and tested: raw bentonite (RB), bentonite thermally activated at 300°C (AB300), and bentonite activated at 400°C (AB400). The raw bentonite was used directly, while the two activated forms were obtained by heating the clay in a muffle furnace at temperatures for 1 hour and 30 minutes respectively. After thermal treatment, the activated samples were cooled in a desiccator and stored in airtight containers for use in the adsorption experiments.

The heavy metal solutions were prepared using analytical-grade zinc nitrate [$Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$] and lead nitrate [$Pb(NO_3)_2$], each dissolved in distilled water to obtain a stock solution with a concentration of 50 ppm (mg/L). A batch adsorption method was used throughout the study. For each test, 50 mL of the metal solution was placed in a 100 mL beaker, to which varying dosages of bentonite (0.5 g, 0.7 g, 0.9 g, and 1.1 g) were added. The mixture was stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer for both contact time which is 30 minutes and 60 minutes to guarantee proper interaction between the metal ions and the bentonite particles (Tadesse, 2022).

Following the stirring process, the mixture was filtered using a vacuum filtration pump to separate the treated water from the bentonite. The filtrates were then analyzed using Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) spectrometry to determine the concentration of residual zinc or lead ions. The percentage removal of each metal was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times 100$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration (ppm) and C_t is the final concentration after treatment. This methodology enabled a systematic comparison of the adsorptive performance of raw and thermally activated bentonite for heavy metal removal (Tadesse, 2022).

3. FINDINGS

This section presents and interprets the experimental findings related to the removal efficiency of zinc and lead using three forms of bentonite clay: raw bentonite (RB), thermally activated at 300°C (AB300), and thermally activated at 400°C (AB400). The experiments were conducted at two contact times (30 and 60 minutes) and four dosage levels (0.5 g, 0.7 g, 0.9 g, and 1.1 g).

Table 1. Heavy metal concentration (mg/l) after adsorption at different conditions

<i>Conditions</i>	<i>0.5 g</i>	<i>0.7 g</i>	<i>0.9 g</i>	<i>1.1 g</i>
<i>Zinc - 30 min – Raw (mg/l)</i>	29.20	27.22	22.52	19.01
<i>Zinc - 30 min - 300 °C (mg/l)</i>	32.90	28.06	22.96	15.94
<i>Zinc - 30 min - 400 °C (mg/l)</i>	28.35	25.48	21.46	12.83
<i>Zinc - 60 min – Raw (mg/l)</i>	26.15	20.37	17.98	14.20
<i>Zinc - 60 min - 300 °C (mg/l)</i>	24.03	22.50	17.03	12.59
<i>Zinc - 60 min - 400 °C (mg/l)</i>	23.35	20.04	16.42	12.03
<i>Lead - 30 min – Raw (mg/l)</i>	22.36	15.92	9.25	1.286
<i>Lead - 30 min - 300 °C (mg/l)</i>	18.71	13.92	2.49	0.10
<i>Lead - 30 min - 400 °C (mg/l)</i>	17.28	10.34	0.73	0.058
<i>Lead - 60 min – Raw (mg/l)</i>	19.32	15.07	9.87	5.19
<i>Lead - 60 min - 300 °C (mg/l)</i>	16.67	13.29	9.22	2.842
<i>Lead - 60 min - 400 °C (mg/l)</i>	15.80	13.22	8.54	0.20

3.1 Zinc Removal Efficiency

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the graph of zinc removal efficiency concerning different dosages at different activation temperatures. For zinc, the removal efficiency increased with both contact time and adsorbent dosage. At 30 minutes, AB400 showed the highest removal efficiency across all dosages, with a maximum of 74.34% at 1.1 g. Raw bentonite has showed lower efficiency, achieving only 61.98% at the same dosage.

At 60 minutes, the zinc removal further improved. AB400 again demonstrated the best performance, with a peak efficiency of 75.94% at 1.1 g. This show that thermal activation, especially at 400 °C has significantly enhances the adsorptive capacity of bentonite for zinc ions, likely due to increased surface area and availability of active sites (Tadesse, 2022).

Figure 1. Graph of zinc removal efficiency vs. bentonite dosage at different activation temperatures at 30 minutes

Figure 2. Graph of zinc removal efficiency vs. bentonite dosage at different activation temperatures at 60 minutes

3.2 Lead Removal Efficiency

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the graph of lead removal efficiency concerning different dosages at different activation temperatures. Lead removal results followed a similar trend but exhibited even higher efficiency overall. At 30 minutes, AB400 achieved 99.88% removal at 1.1 g, while raw bentonite reached 97.43%. At 60 minutes, the efficiency of AB400 has reached 99.60%, maintaining its effective removal. Even at lower dosages, thermally activated bentonite outperformed the raw form. The high removal rates of lead, especially using AB400, suggest a strong affinity between the bentonite's active sites and Pb^{2+} ions.

Figure 3. Graph of lead removal efficiency vs. bentonite dosage at different activation temperatures at 30 minutes

Figure 4. Graph of lead removal efficiency vs. bentonite dosage at different activation temperatures at 60 minutes

3.3 Comparative Performance and Implications

The comparative analysis of the three bentonite types revealed that thermal activation significantly enhanced the adsorptive performance of bentonite, particularly at 400°C. At both 30- and 60-minutes contact time, the bentonite activated at 400°C consistently outperformed both raw bentonite and the sample activated at 300°C in removing zinc and lead from aqueous solutions. This improvement resulted from the increase in surface area and availability of active sites due to thermal treatment (Selim et al., 2020). The efficiency of metal removal has improved with higher bentonite dosage, which provided more surface area for ion exchange and adsorption (Ibigbami et al., 2022). Zinc removal efficiency peaked at 75.94% with 1.1 g of AB400 at 60 minutes, while lead removal reached as high as 99.6% under the same conditions. Out of all conditions, lead ions were more effectively adsorbed than zinc ions, these is due to their larger ionic radius and stronger binding affinity with the bentonite surface.

These findings suggest that thermally activated bentonite when treated at 400°C, is a highly effective, low-cost, and environmentally sustainable adsorbent for treating water contaminated with heavy metals. Due to the activation process is simple and uses easily available natural materials, this method is a great option for expanding on a larger scale especially in areas that don't have access to advanced water treatment systems (Hamad et al., 2024). The enhanced performance of AB400 also presents strong commercialization potential for industrial and municipal wastewater treatment applications, offering a viable alternative to more expensive synthetic adsorbents.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of this study clearly address the effectiveness of bentonite clay as an adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals especially zinc and lead from its liquid state. The adsorption efficiency was considerably affected by three key factors: the form of bentonite used (raw or thermally activated), the contact time, and the adsorbent dosage. Among the three types of bentonites tested, the sample thermally activated at 400°C (AB400) consistently exhibited the highest removal efficiency for both zinc and lead ions. This can be contributed to the structural changes affected by thermal treatment, such as increased porosity, larger surface area, and improved availability of active adsorption sites (Tadesse, 2022).

As the contact time increased from 30 to 60 minutes, a clear improvement in removal efficiency was observed, it shows that more time allowed the metal ions to interact with and be adsorbed onto the bentonite surface. Similarly, increasing the dosage from 0.5 g to 1.1 g provided a larger number of adsorption sites, which further enhanced metal uptake. The adsorption performance of lead was consistently higher than that of zinc across all bentonite types and conditions. This is likely due to the larger ionic radius and stronger electrostatic attraction of lead ions, which allow for more effective interaction with the bentonite surface (Chai et al., 2017).

The performance trend in this study matches what previous research has shown—thermally activated bentonite works better at removing metals because heating it removes volatile components and structural water, making the surface more porous and active for adsorption (Tadesse, 2022). These findings confirm the suitability of locally available bentonite, especially after simple thermal treatment, as a sustainable and cost-effective solution for heavy metal removal in water treatment processes. The high adsorption capacities and removal efficiencies achieved particularly with AB400 has highlight the potential for practical application and commercialization of this treatment method in industrial and municipal wastewater management.

5. CONCLUSION

This study successfully indicated the potential of bentonite clay especially in its thermally activated forms, for the efficient removal of zinc and lead from aqueous solutions. The experimental results confirmed that thermal activation significantly enhances the adsorptive performance of bentonite, with the sample treated at 400°C (AB400) showing the highest removal efficiencies. Lead ions were more effectively removed than zinc ions under the same conditions due to their stronger interaction with the bentonite surface. Increasing the adsorbent dosage and contact time further improved the removal performance confirming the importance of process optimization. These findings support the feasibility of using thermally activated bentonite as cost effective, widely available, and environmentally friendly material make it for heavy metal remediation in wastewater treatment applications.

References

- Chai, W., Huang, Y., Su, S., Han, G., Liu, J., & Cao, Y. (2017). Adsorption behavior of zn(ii) onto natural minerals in wastewater. a comparative study of bentonite and kaolinite. *Physicochemical Problems of Mineral Processing*, 53(1), 264–278. <https://doi.org/10.5277/ppmp170122>
- Hamad, H. N., Idrus, S., Yusuf, B., Jamali, N. S., Ahsan, A., Suhartini, S., & Wahab, A. M. A. (2024). Optimized Bentonite Clay Adsorbents for Methylene Blue Removal. *Processes*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr12040738>
- Ibigbami, T. B., Adeola, A. O., Olawade, D. B., Ore, O. T., Isaac, B. O., & Sunkanmi, A. A. (2022). Pristine and activated bentonite for toxic metal removal from wastewater. *Water Practice and Technology*, 17(3), 784–797. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2022.018>
- Munir, N., Jahangeer, M., Bouyahya, A., Omari, N. el, Ghchime, R., Balahbib, A., Aboulaghras, S., Mahmood, Z., Akram, M., Shah, S. M. A., Mikolaychik, I. N., Derkho, M., Rebezov, M., Venkidasamy, B., Thiruvengadam, M., & Shariati, M. A. (2022). Heavy metal contamination of natural foods is a serious health issue: A review. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 14, Issue 1). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010161>
- Ouyang, D., Zhuo, Y., Hu, L., Zeng, Q., Hu, Y., & He, Z. (2019). Research on the adsorption behavior of heavy metal ions by porous material prepared with silicate tailings. *Minerals*, 9(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/min9050291>
- Pizutti, J. T., dos Santos, R. de C., Hemkemeier, M., & Piccin, J. S. (2019). Electrocoagulation coupled adsorption for anaerobic wastewater post-treatment and reuse purposes. *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 160, 144–152. <https://doi.org/10.5004/dwt.2019.24365>
- Selim, K. A., Rostom, M., Youssef, M. A., Abdel-Khalek, N. A., Khalek, M. A. A., & Hassan, E. S. R. E. (2020). Surface modified bentonite mineral as a sorbent for Pb²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions removal from aqueous solutions. *Physicochemical Problems of Mineral Processing*, 56(6), 145–157. <https://doi.org/10.37190/PPMP/127833>
- Tadesse, S. H. (2022). Application of Ethiopian bentonite for water treatment containing zinc. *Emerging Contaminants*, 8, 113–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emcon.2022.02.002>
- Wang, P., Shen, X., Qiu, S., Zhang, L., Ma, Y., & Liang, J. (2024). Clay-Based Materials for Heavy Metals Adsorption: Mechanisms, Advancements, and Future Prospects in Environmental Remediation. In *Crystals* (Vol. 14, Issue 12). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst14121046>